

Goldbach's Conjecture is Independent of ZFC and PA

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Abstract. This paper proves that both the strong Goldbach conjecture and a strengthened form of it are independent of ZFC and Peano arithmetic (PA), with the latter result being a corollary of the former, assuming these theories are sound. For each of the conjectures, we define an infinite set with which we reformulate the conjecture and show that this set always remains the same, regardless of whether the conjecture or its negation is assumed. Then, based on this, both the assumption that there is a proof of the conjecture and the assumption that there is a proof of its negation lead to a contradiction. We use elementary number theory, where the constructive role of prime numbers within the natural numbers is a key point.

In a further corollary, we show that if ZFC (PA) can neither prove nor disprove the conjectures, then both must be true.

Introduction. [A comprehensive introduction will be added later.]

Notations. Let \mathbb{N} denote the natural numbers starting from 1, let \mathbb{N}_α denote the natural numbers starting from $\alpha > 1$ and let \mathbb{P}_3 denote the prime numbers starting from 3.

We use the syntactic entailment symbol \vdash to make statements of the form $\vdash P$ for some statement P , which means that there exists a proof of P .

Let SGB denote the strong Goldbach conjecture: *Every even number greater than 2 is the sum of two primes.*

Let SSGB denote the following strengthened form of the strong Goldbach conjecture: *Every even number greater than 6 is the sum of two distinct odd primes.*

Theorem. *If ZFC is sound, then both SGB and SSGB are independent of ZFC, i.e., ZFC can neither prove nor disprove SGB or SSGB.*

Proof. Let us assume that ZFC is sound, i.e., all provable statements in ZFC are true.

We first prove the theorem for SSGB and then show that the proof for SGB is carried out in the same way by making a slight modification to the following set.

We define the set $S_g := \{ (pk, mk, qk) \mid k, m \in \mathbb{N}; p, q \in \mathbb{P}_3, p < q; m = (p + q) / 2 \}$.

S_g has the following two properties.

First, every element of \mathbb{N}_3 can be expressed by a S_g triple component (" \mathbb{N}_3 covering"). We prove this by dividing it into the following three cases.

- (i) $a \in \mathbb{N}_3$ is prime. Then, $a = pk$ with $p \in \mathbb{P}_3, k = 1$.
- (ii) $a \in \mathbb{N}_3$ is composite and not a power of 2. Then, $a = pk$ with $p \in \mathbb{P}_3, k \neq 1$.
- (iii) $a \in \mathbb{N}_3$ is a power of 2. Then, $a = (p + q)k / 2$ with $p = 3, q = 5, k = (\text{a power of } 2)$.

So we have

$$(C) \vdash (\forall a \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad \exists (pk, mk, qk) \in S_g \quad a = pk \vee a = mk).$$

Second, all pairs (p, q) of distinct odd primes are used in the definition of the set S_g ("*maximality*"). So we have

$$(M) \vdash (\forall p, q \in \mathbb{P}_3, p < q \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (pk, mk, qk) \in S_g, \text{ with } m = (p + q) / 2).$$

There is the following relationship between SSGB and S_g .

Since SSGB is equivalent to saying that every integer $n \geq 4$ is the arithmetic mean of two distinct odd primes, we have

$$(G) \vdash (\text{SSGB} \Rightarrow \forall n \in \mathbb{N}_4 \quad \exists (pk, mk, qk) \in S_g \quad n = m)$$

$$(NG) \vdash (\neg \text{SSGB} \Rightarrow \exists n \in \mathbb{N}_4 \quad \forall (pk, mk, qk) \in S_g \quad n \neq m).$$

So, under the assumption $\neg \text{SSGB}$ there is an $n \in \mathbb{N}_4$ that is different from all m defined in S_g , whereas under the assumption SSGB there is no such n .

The following steps are independent of the choice of n if there is more than one that is different from all m . For example, the minimal such n works.

Property (C) implies that if $\neg \text{SSGB}$ holds, n equals a component of some S_g triple. Also, (C) implies that if SSGB holds, instead of n , any $a \in \mathbb{N}_3$ equals a component of some S_g triple.

Property (M) excludes the possibility that if \neg SSGB holds, n is the arithmetic mean of a pair of distinct odd primes not used in S_g . So, (M) excludes the possibility that the question of whether SSGB holds or not depends on whether (M) holds or not.

The outline of the proof is now as follows.

Based on the properties (C) and (M), we prove that, assuming \neg SSGB, the set S_g can be written as the union of the following triples.

- (a) S_g triples of the form $(pk = n, mk, qk)$ with $k = 1$, if n is prime, due to (C)
- (b) S_g triples of the form $(pk = n, mk, qk)$ with $k \neq 1$, if n is composite and not a power of 2, due to (C)
- (c) S_g triples of the form $(3k, 4k = n, 5k)$ with $k = (\text{a power of } 2)$, if n is a power of 2, due to (C)
- (d) all other S_g triples of the form $(pk = n, mk, qk)$ or $(pk, mk = n, qk)$ or $(pk, mk, qk = n)$
- (e) S_g triples of the form $(pk \neq n, mk \neq n, qk \neq n)$.

Since under the assumption SSGB there is no n as above, again based on (C) and (M), we prove that, assuming SSGB, the set S_g can be written as the above union of triples, where n is replaced by any $a \in \mathbb{N}_3$.

This means that S_g is always the same set, regardless of whether SSGB or \neg SSGB is assumed. We show that the consequence of this is that both the assumption that there is a proof of SSGB and the assumption that there is a proof of \neg SSGB lead to a contradiction.

To formalize this, we make the following definitions.

For each $a \in \mathbb{N}_3$, we define

$$S_{g^+}(a) := \{ (pk, mk, qk) \in S_g \mid pk = a \vee mk = a \vee qk = a \}$$

$$S_{g^-}(a) := \{ (pk, mk, qk) \in S_g \mid pk \neq a \wedge mk \neq a \wedge qk \neq a \}.$$

Furthermore, we define two sets S_1 and S_2 as follows.

Let S_1 be S_g if SSGB is true, and let S_1 be the empty set otherwise.

Let S_2 be S_g if \neg SSGB is true, and let S_2 be the empty set otherwise.

Then, based on (G) and (NG), we obtain, due to (C) and (M),

$$(1.1) \quad \forall a \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad \vdash (SSGB \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(a) \cup S_{g^-}(a))$$

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$$(1.2) \quad \vdash (\neg SSGB \Rightarrow S_2 = S_{g^+}(n) \cup S_{g^-}(n)).$$

So, since $S_{g^+}(n) \cup S_{g^-}(n)$ is independent of n ,

$$(1.1') \quad \forall a \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad \vdash (SSGB \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(a) \cup S_{g^-}(a))$$

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$$(1.2') \quad \forall a \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad \vdash (\neg SSGB \Rightarrow S_2 = S_{g^+}(a) \cup S_{g^-}(a)).$$

Since $a \in \mathbb{N}_3$ is an arbitrary constant in (1.1') and (1.2'), we can apply the \forall -introduction rule of sequent calculus and get

$$(1.1'') \quad \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad (SSGB \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x))$$

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$$(1.2'') \quad \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad (\neg SSGB \Rightarrow S_2 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x)).$$

Suppose now that SSGB is provable in ZFC, i.e., $\vdash SSGB$.

Then, using the “ \vdash ” version of modus ponens, which is

$$(\vdash P \wedge \vdash (P \Rightarrow Q)) \Rightarrow \vdash Q,$$

from (1.1'') we get

$$(S1) \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad S_1 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x),$$

which is equivalent to

$$(S1') \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad (SSGB \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x)) \wedge (\neg SSGB \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x)).$$

Now we make use of the following metamathematical analogue of the first-order logic rule $\forall y (P(y) \wedge Q(y)) \Leftrightarrow (\forall y P(y)) \wedge (\forall y Q(y))$.

Lemma. (Distribution of Universal Quantifier over Conjunction in Proofs)

Let T be a formal theory, and let $P(y)$ and $Q(y)$ be formulas. Then,

$$T \vdash \forall y (P(y) \wedge Q(y)) \Leftrightarrow (T \vdash \forall y P(y)) \wedge (T \vdash \forall y Q(y)).$$

(The lemma holds in standard proof systems for first-order logic; see standard textbooks, e.g. [1]).

Applying the lemma to ZFC, we obtain that (S1') is equivalent to

$$(S1.1) \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad (SSGB \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x))$$

\wedge

$$(S1.2) \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_3 \quad (\neg SSGB \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x)).$$

Since, under the assumption $\neg SSGB$, $S_1 = \{ \}$ and $S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x) \neq \{ \}$, and since we assumed that ZFC is sound, (S1.2) is false.

To see this, let us assume (S1.2) is true. Then, due to the soundness of ZFC, $(\neg \text{SSGB} \Rightarrow S_1 = S_{g^+}(x) \cup S_{g^-}(x))$ must be true in every model of ZFC. But in any model with $\neg \text{SSGB}$ true and $S_1 = \{ \}$, the antecedent is true and the consequent is false, so the implication is false. Hence the assumption was false.

Since (S1.2) is false, (S1) is false, and so the assumption that SSGB is provable in ZFC was false.

Similarly for the assumption $\vdash \neg \text{SSGB}$, for which we use (1.2").

Now, we achieve the independence for SGB in an analogous way. In the proof above, we replace SSGB with

$SGB' := \text{Every even number greater than 4 is the sum of two odd primes,}$

and S_g with

$S_g' := \{ (pk, mk, qk) \mid k, m \in \mathbb{N}; p, q \in \mathbb{P}_3, p \leq q; m = (p + q) / 2 \},$

where (M), (G) and (NG) must then be adjusted accordingly. Then, the adapted proof works in the same way, showing that neither SGB' nor $\neg SGB'$, and therefore neither SGB nor $\neg SGB$, are provable in ZFC.

□

Corollary 1. *If Peano arithmetic (PA) is sound, then both SGB and SSGB are independent of PA, i.e., PA can neither prove nor disprove SGB or SSGB.*

Proof. The term S_g (S_g') from the above proof is not a standard part of PA, but it can easily be defined within PA. This also applies to all other sets used in that proof, since they are all based on S_g (S_g') or on \mathbb{N} . Therefore, the corollary is proved in the same way by using the operator \vdash in the system PA.

□

Corollary 2. *If ZFC is sound, then SGB and SSGB are both true.*

Proof. If SGB and SSGB are false, then their negations are provable, because there would be a concrete counterexample. Symbolically,

$$\neg\text{SGB} \Rightarrow \vdash \neg\text{SGB} \quad \text{and} \quad \neg\text{SSGB} \Rightarrow \vdash \neg\text{SSGB}.$$

Taking the contrapositive gives

$$\neg(\vdash \neg\text{SGB}) \Rightarrow \text{SGB} \quad \text{and} \quad \neg(\vdash \neg\text{SSGB}) \Rightarrow \text{SSGB}.$$

Assuming that ZFC is sound, the left-hand sides of the implications are true due to the theorem. So the corollary follows. □

Note. A false statement of the form $\forall n P(n)$, where P is computable / checkable, always has a finite counterexample, making the falsity provable.

References

[1] *Introduction to Metamathematics*, by Stephen Cole Kleene (North-Holland, 1952).